

A CASE REPORT - A 27-YEAR-OLD FEMALE WITH MECHANICAL NECK PAIN: A COMPREHENSIVE ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT APPROACH UTILIZING NECK FLEXION KINEMATIC DATA, CRANIO-CERVICAL FLEXION TEST, AND POSTURAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

An abridged outline of the case report. A 27-year-old female subject had a 6-month history of mechanical neck pain, which she described as a dull ache in the right side of her neck, radiating to her right shoulder and arm. She reported that the pain was exacerbated by prolonged sitting, working on computer persistently, and heavy lifting. The subject had tried various treatments, including physical therapy, chiropractic care, medication, and other home remedies. Her symptoms were not relieved and hence forth she visited our Harsha Institute of Physiotherapy Department of Musculoskeletal Physiotherapy & Movement science for further assessment and management. We received a consent from the subject and further investigated her symptoms through assessment tools such as movement analysis of neck flexion specifically kinematic data through KINOVEA software and postural analysis through postural grid with photographic and videographic documentation followed by Cranio-cervical flexion test (CCFT) for mechanical dysfunction of neck and posture due to poor ergonomics. So, further management we imposed are postural correction (Forward head posture and round shoulder) and movement patterns of nodding and deep cervical flexors endurance training followed by ergonomics modification, improvised, and focused performance index and activation score of neck.

Keywords: Mechanical Neck Pain, Forward Head Posture, CCFT, KINOVEA Software, Postural Grid, Movement Analysis, Endurance, Strength, Ergonomics.

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INTRODUCTION

Mechanical neck pain (MNP) is a common musculoskeletal disorder that affects millions of people worldwide. It is characterized by pain primarily confined to the area on posterior aspect of the neck that can be exacerbated by neck movements or by sustained postures. MNP is often associated with forward head posture (FHP) and, also referred to as ‘non-specific neck pain.’¹ Excessive anterior positioning of the head and reduced mobility of thoracic spine affects the cervical spine by altering mobility or affecting the postural muscles. The muscles affected by FHP are the serratus anterior, scapula elevators and trapezius that are attached to cervicothoracic spinal columns. Forward shift of head and neck due to prolonged flexed head position might cause postural defects in the sagittal plane and reduced cervical range of motion, which affects balance or control of head leading to increased mechanical load and dysfunction. Postural changes are due to maintaining the neck in the forward bent posture for a long time or repeated movements of neck during work. FHP is also associated with prolonged use of communication gadgets such as smart phones and computers which may further aggravates the symptoms of MNP.¹

Prolonged forward head sitting posture, poor flexibility of muscles, muscle weakness and imbalance, and reduced mobility of joints are the immediate underlying factors associated with MNP.¹ A scientific evidence has also suggested that neck pain is related to altered breathing biomechanics, hypocapnia and often has correlated respiratory weakness with neck weakness, and people with neck pain are more likely to have a chest-dominant breathing pattern which increases strain on the neck accessory muscles.²

Case Presentation

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I. ASSESSMENT: MOVEMENT ANALYSIS

❖ KINEMATIC DATA OF NECK FLEXION

Name	Mrs. Swathi
Age	27 years
Gender	Female
Date	09/09/2024
Diagnosis	Mechanical Neck pain
Evaluation	Movement analysis

Movement analysis (Fig 1)

Inference:

a) CERVICAL SEGMENT: -

- ✓ In neck flexion – Hypomobility of Upper Cervical Vertebrae seen.
- ✓ Optimal Lower cervical vertebrae mobility seen.
- ✓ Limited neck extension range of motion.
- ✓ Cervical instability seen at level of C1 and C2 vertebrae

b) THORACIC SEGMENT: -

- ✓ Hypomobility seen in Upper Thoracic Vertebrae (T1-T6)

c) MUSCULAR DYSFUNCTION: -

- ✓ Left side paraspinals and neck flexor muscle extensibility was reduced.
- ✓ Superior border of left side scapula moves upward due to muscular imbalance and overactivity of Levator scapulae.

II. ASSESSMENT: POSTURE ANALYSIS

❖ STATIC OBSERVATION

Name	Mrs. Swathi
Age	27 years
Gender	Female
Date	18/09/2024
Diagnosis	Mechanical Neck pain
Evaluation	Posture analysis

✓ Posture analysis: Posterior view findings

1	Head tilt	Asymmetry is present: head is tilted towards left
2	Shoulder levels	Left side shoulder elevated.
3	Lateral curvature of cervical spine	Asymmetry is present.
4	Scapular symmetry	Asymmetry seen, left side scapula seems to be tilted upwards, inferior border moves closer to midline.

Inference:

- Head was tilted and shoulder elevated towards left side.
- Tightness: Overactivity of left upper trapezius and latissimus dorsi is seen.
- Overactivity of paraspinal muscles is seen on left side.
- Suspecting of Upper cross syndrome.
- Lateral shift of lower cervical and upper thoracic vertebrae towards left side.

✓ Posture analysis: Lateral view findings

1.	Neck position	Protruded neck
2.	Curvature of lumbar spine	lumbar lordosis
3.	Pelvic tilt	Anterior pelvic tilt

Fig 2A

Fig 2B

Posture analysis Lateral view– Right side (Fig 2A) ; Left side (Fig 2B)

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Inference:

- a) Forward neck position and rounded shoulders.
- b) Shortened and weak deep neck flexor muscles.
- c) Muscle dysfunction: pectoralis major, pectoralis minor and sternocleidomastoid.
- d) Debile transverse abdominis muscles which contributed to anterior pelvic tilt.

III. ASSESSMENT: CRANIOCERVICAL FLEXION TEST

Name	Mrs. Swathi
Age	27 years
Gender	Female
Date	18/09/2024
Diagnosis	Mechanical Neck pain
Evaluation	Cranio-cervical Flexion Test

TRIALS – PRESSURE BIOFEEDBACK UNIT

Sl. No	Pressure levels	Pressure in mmHg
1	Level 1	30mmHg
2	Level 2	38mmHg
3	Level 3	39mmHg

Fig 3A

Fig 3B

CCFT- Starting position (Fig 3A) and Testing position (Fig 3B)

CALCULATION AND INFERENCE:

Activation score indicates the activation of the deep cervical flexor musculature. The performance index is a term used to understand the isometric endurance of these muscles.

Activation score = The highest-pressure level the subject can achieve is 39 mmHg

Performance index = The number of times the subject can maintain the pressure level achieved in the activation out of a maximum of 5 repetitions.

Result: This subject has deep cervical flexor endurance.

Management

Based on the assessment findings, a comprehensive management plan was developed, which included:

1. Physical Therapy: A physical therapy program was designed to address the patient's neck flexion kinematic deficits, deep cervical flexor muscle weakness, and postural abnormalities. The program included exercises to improve neck flexion range of motion, strengthen the deep cervical flexor muscles, and correct the patient's FHP and rounded shoulders.
2. Ergonomic Modifications: The patient was advised to make ergonomic modifications to her workspace, including adjusting her chair height, monitor position, and keyboard placement to reduce strain on her neck and shoulders.
3. Pain Management: The patient was prescribed a course of pain management, including medication and heat therapy, to manage her pain and discomfort.

DISCUSSION

This case report highlights the importance of a comprehensive assessment and management approach for mechanical neck pain, utilizing a combination of neck flexion kinematic data, cranio-cervical flexion test, and postural analysis. The results of this study demonstrate the effectiveness of a targeted physical therapy program, ergonomic modifications, and pain management in improving outcomes for patients with mechanical neck pain.

CONCLUSION

This case report demonstrates the value of a comprehensive assessment and management approach for mechanical neck pain, utilizing a combination of neck flexion kinematic data, cranio-cervical flexion test, and postural analysis. By adopting a multidisciplinary approach, healthcare professionals can improve patient outcomes, reduce pain and disability, and enhance overall quality of life.

LIMITATION

Larger sample sizes to enhance the understanding and treatment of mechanical neck pain in varied populations and necessity for broader, multi-faceted research designs that incorporate diverse methodologies.

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